

Magnetically Guided Virotherapy for Photodynamic Therapy to Over-come Multi Drug Resistance in Breast Cancer Cells

Z.-X. Liao

Institute of Medical Science and Technology, National Sun Yat-sen University, Taiwan

Abstract:

Chemotherapy represents a conventional treatment for many cancers at different stages either solely prescribed or concomitant to surgery and/or radiotherapy. However, treatment is tempered in instances of acquired drug resistance in response to either chemo- or targeted-therapy, leading to therapeutic failure. To overcome this challenge, many studies focus on how cancer cells manipulate their genomes and metabolism to prevent drug influx and/or facilitate efflux of accumulated chemo drugs. Herein We previously developed 'controllable' virus for either recombinant adeno-associated virus serotype 2 (AAV2) or lentivirus via chemical conjugation with iron oxide nano-particles that could be directed with magnetic fields. Furthermore, a gene of the photosensitive protein or short hairpin RNA (shRNA) was introduced into the AAV2 or lentivirus genome to enable photo-dynamic therapy (PDT). or RNA interference (RNAi). In the case of PDT, irradiation with a specific light bandwidth generates reactive oxygen species leading to irreversible DNA damage and cell killing via an apoptotic pathway^{8,10}; offering additional options in cancer treatment. Here, we present an improvement to this previous work that promotes viral transduction in chemo drug resistant-MCF-7 (CDRMCF-7) cells under magnetic field, and express the KillerRed (KR) protein in transduced cells for light-triggered virotherapy (AAV2-KR) (Figure 1).

Keywords:

Virotherapy, recombinant adeno-associated virus serotype 2, iron oxide nanoparticles, bioconjugation, photo-dynamic therapy.

Figure 1: Light-triggered virotherapy. Schematic representation of light-triggered virotherapy to a chemo drug resistance-cancer cell. a) AAV2 carrying the KillerRed gene and conjugated with magnetic iron oxide nano-particles can be specifically directed with magnetic fields. b) Viral delivery transduces the KillerRed gene inside cells leading to expression of the KillerRed protein. c) Irradiation of KillerRed with laser light produces reactive oxygen species (ROS). d) ROS lead to DNA double strand breaks and apoptosis.

References:

1. Liao, Z.-X., Kempson I.M., Fa, Y.-C., Liu, M.-C., Hsieh, L.-C., Huang, K.-Y., Wang, F.-W. (2017) Magnetically Guided Viral Transduction of Gene-Based Sensitization for Localized Photodynamic Therapy To Overcome Multidrug Resistance in Breast Cancer Cells, *Bioconjugate Chem.*, 28, 1702-1708.
2. Tseng, S.-J., Huang, K.-Y., Kempson I.M., Kuo, S.-H., Liu, M.-C., Yang, S.-C., Liao, Z.-X., Yang, P.-C. (2016), Remote Control Of Light-Triggered Virotherapy, *ACS Nano*, 10, 10339-10346.

Targeting Tumor Microenvironment by Bioreduction-Activated Nanoparticles for Light-Triggered Virotherapy

S.-J. Tseng

Graduate Institute of Oncology, National Taiwan University College of Medicine, Taiwan

Abstract:

Solid tumors characteristically display higher levels of lactate production due to anaerobic metabolism of glucose. Meanwhile, the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has approved virotherapy for use in cancer treatment, however systemic administration remains as a particular challenge. Here we report exploitation of tumor lactate production in designing a hypoxia-responsive carrier, self-assembled from hyaluronic acid (HA) conjugated with 6-(2-nitroimidazole)hexylamine, for localized re-release of recombinant adeno-associated virus serotype 2 (AAV2). The carrier is loaded with lactate oxidase (LOX) and is permeable to small molecules such as the lactate that accumulates in the tumor. Subsequently, LOX oxidizes the lactate to pyruvate inside the carrier, accompanied by internal lowering of oxygen partial pressure. Bio-reduction of the 2-nitroimidazole of the HA conjugated with 6-(2-nitroimidazole)hexylamine converts it into a hydrophilic moiety and electro-statically dissociates the carrier and virus. Efficacious and specific delivery was proven by transduction of a photosensitive protein (KillerRed) enabling significant limitation in tumor growth in vivo with photodynamic therapy. An approximate 2.44-fold reduction in tumor weight was achieved after a 2-week course, compared with control groups. Furthermore, conjugation of the AAV2 with iron oxide nanoparticles ('Magnetized' AAV2) facilitated magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) tracking of the virus in vivo. Taken together, the solid tumor microenvironment promotes bioreduction of the lactate-responsive carrier, providing rapid and specific delivery of AAV2 for light-triggered virotherapy via systemic administration (Figure 1).

Keywords:

Virotherapy, tumor microenvironment, nano-particle, lactate oxidase, photo-dynamic therapy.

Figure 1: Concept of lactate-responsive nanoparticle assembled from hyaluronic acid conjugated with 6-(2-nitroimidazole)-hexylamine loaded with AAV2 and lactate oxidase (LOX). The carrier is permeable to lactate which has elevated concentrations in hypoxic tumour microenvironments. LOX oxidises lactate to create a bioreducing environment within the carrier, converting the hydrophobic 2-nitroimidazole to be hydrophilic, and electrostatically dissociating the carrier and the payload.

References:

1. Tseng, S.-J., Kempson I.M., Huang, K.-Y., Li, H.-J., Fa, Y.-C., Ho, Y.-C., Liao, Z.-X., Yang, P.-C. (2018) Targeting Tumor Microenvironment by Bioreduction-Activated Nanoparticles for Light-Triggered Virotherapy, *ACS Nano*, 12, 9894-9902.
2. Tseng, S.-J., Huang, K.-Y., Kempson I.M., Kuo, S.-H., Liu, M.-C., Yang, S.-C., Liao, Z.-X., Yang, P.-C. (2016), Remote Control Of Light-Triggered Virotherapy, *ACS Nano*, 10, 10339-10346.

Comparative Study of Nanocatalysts FeS₂ and FeSe₂ for Molecular Hydrogen Evolution Reaction

Shwetharani R, D H Nagaraju, R Geetha Balakrishna

Centre for Nano and Material Sciences, Jain University, India

Email: dhnagu@gmail.com, br.geetha@jainuniversity.ac.in

Abstract:

Hydrogen generation through electrocatalytic water reduction using copious and scalable electrocatalyst is one of the potential methods to produce clean energy. Transition metal dichalcogenides with appropriate band potential have been demonstrated as potential electrocatalysts for hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). Here in we have synthesized nanostructured FeS₂ and FeSe₂ that possess defined and irregular shaped flower like morphology using solvothermal reduction method. X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) confirms the pyrite FeS₂ (iron disulfide) and orthorhombic phase FeSe₂ (iron diselenide) and compared it's HER catalytic performance. FeSe₂ exhibited lower over potential of 113 mV with a current of 2 mA/cm² (10 mA/cm² current at 244 mV) compared to FeS₂ with over potential 453 mV. The improved catalytic behavior of FeSe₂ can be attributed to favourable bond strength between selenide and hydrogen (276 kJ/mol) which is about 87 kJ/mol lesser than FeS₂ (363 kJ/mol).

Keywords:

FeS₂, Electrocatalyst, H₂ evolution, FeSe₂, Transition metal dichalcogenides

Agrinotechnology : Application of nanotechnologies in agriculture and allied sciences

T.N.V.K.V.Prasad

Nanotechnology Laboratory, Institute of Frontier Technologies, Regional Agricultural research Station, Acharya N G Ranga Agricultural University, INDIA

Abstract:

Nanotechnologies dealing with the agriculture and allied sciences could be termed as “Agri-nanotechnology”. Evidence based effects of nanoscale materials (size between 1-99 nm in at least one dimension with quantum confinement) on the productivity enhancement, quality, disease resistance, food packaging, soil remediation and water purification hasened the nano-technology research programmes and created lot of enthusiasm amongst the interdisciplinary researchers. Delivery of zinc through a 25 nm sized, well defined nanoscale zinc oxide (n-ZnO) material (Figure 1) twice (foliar application) at relatively lower doses (15 times less) recorded 29% higher yield in peanut crop whereas in maize 15% enhancement of yield has been recorded compared to its bulk counterpart. Moreover, significant grain zinc concentration in maize (36 ppm) has been observed with the application of 100 ppm of n-ZnO but significant yield has been recorded with 400 ppm of n-ZnO application which leads to a concept of designer agri-products. Nearly 18% enhancement in brix content has been recorded in sorghum biomass with the application of n-ZnO, nanoscale calcium oxide (n-CaO) and nanoscale magnesium oxide (n-MgO) and inturn influenced the enhancement of bioethanol production. It has been proved using solution culture method that n-CaO could transport through phloem in peanut points to the foliar application of nanoscale calcium on agricultural crops. Aoin coated silver nanoparticles have been proved to be effective in containing bovine mastitis in milking animals. Deltametharin and neem coated silver nanoparticles were significantly effective in controlling the ticks. Thus nanotechnologies have significant impact on re-orientation of the agriculture and allied sciences and were promising in attaining agricultural sustainability and global food security.

Keywords:

Nanotechnology, agriculture, animal sciences, yield, grain zinc content, bovine mastitis, bio-ethanol

Figure 1: Transmission electron micrograph (bar scale 100 nm) (TEM) showing the n-ZnO particles with mean size of 25 nm and which was used to deliver the zinc in peanut, maize and soghum crops. Agglomeration of the particles was due to the absence of protecting ligands on the sur-face

Characterization of Neutron detectors based on ^3He

Anas Shehu¹, Usman Abubakar²

Email: Anasbello23@gmail.com ¹, usmanabubakar67@gmail.com ²

Abstract:

The purpose of this project is to study the characteristics of ^3He based neutron detectors. An AmBe neutron generator in a water moderator was used to produce thermal neutrons. The detectors characterization is observed by studying the pulse height resolution, detection efficiency, epithermal neutron response, gamma-ray sensitivity and effect of orientation. The optimum operating conditions of these detectors were investigated by varying the high voltage and shaping time. Pulse-height resolution (%) and intrinsic efficiency (%) of all detectors were found after setting the optimum operation condition of each detector. The best output spectrum is found the detector no. 6 which has 7.812452335% and 4.829427283% for the pulse-height resolution and the intrinsic efficiency respectively. The experiment shows that a gamma exposure rate of ^{60}Co which is lower than 4.78 mR/h does not affect the ability to discriminate gamma rays and neutrons of ^3He based neutron detector. Finally, the intrinsic efficiency (%) of two different source-detector orientations was investigated.

Interaction of light with plasmonic nanoparticles and their applications

Avesh Kumar^{1,2}, R. P. Singh², A. Taneja³

¹School of Physical Sciences, Jawaharlal Nehru University, India

²Physical Research Laboratory, Navrangpura, India

³Department of Chemistry, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University, India

Abstract:

Interaction of light with plasmonic nanoparticles whose wavelength is of the order of interacting light wavelength, have new physics and applications in electronics, optics and optoelectronics. When the light of wavelength corresponding to the surface plasmon resonance absorption propagates through a nonlinear medium metal nanoparticles strongly absorb visible light due to their surface plasmon resonance in which the conducting electrons undergo a collective excitation induced by electric field of visible light. This enhances the local electric field near and on the surface of metal nanoparticles. The enhancement of local electric field within the metal nanoparticles, leads to the formation of an electromagnetic wave. This wave induces a huge field on the particle surface strongly polarizing the atoms of the molecules adsorbed. As the electrons of the atoms vibrate around their center of mass, the induced dipole moment oscillates at the wave frequency. This will affect the density, velocity and plasmonic oscillations of the electronic clouds of each nanoparticle which will improve self-focusing property of the light propagating through a nonlinear media. Self-focusing can be tuned by controlling size and shape of nanostructures that can play a significant role in medical purposes, LEDs, lasers, sensor, solar cell, photovoltaic, photocatalysis and other applications. The Ag@Au nanoparticles are used so that the plasmon resonance corresponding to excitation wavelength can be systematically tuned by varying the thickness of the Au-shell. This can help in increased stability and trapping capability of plasmonic nanoparticles that will boost the development of numerous applications in science and technology.

Keywords:

Nanocomposites, light matter interaction, surface plasmon resonance, local electric field.

Figure 1: Diffraction pattern of CW laser beam (532 nm) passing through the Au nanoparticles solution.

Synthesis Of Copper Oxide(CuO) And Cobalt Oxide(Co3O4) Nanoparticles For Supercapacitor Applications

D.Vandana Reddy¹, T.Bala Narsaiah²

¹ PG student, Department of Chemical Engineering, JNTUA, India.

² Professor, Department of Chemical Engineering, JNTUA, India.

Email: ¹dvandanareddy@gmail.com, ²balutumma.chemengg@jntua.ac.in

Abstract:

Nanotechnology is applied in pharmaceutical, electronics, health care, food and feed, biomedical science, drug and gene delivery, environmental health, chemical industry, energy science, cosmetics, mechanics and space industries. Metal oxides play a very important role in many areas of physics, chemistry, and materials science. Copper oxide and Cobalt oxide have great catalytic activities can be applied to biosensors and electrochemical sensors, electrochemical Supercapacitors, as a semiconductors used in solar energy transformation. In the present work, copper oxide and Cobalt oxide nanoparticles are synthesized by using sol-gel process. The structure and morphology of the prepared samples are characterized by XRD, FESEM, EDAX and DLS analysis. The XRD patterns and EDX spectra showed that particles are highly pure, crystalline and nanosized. The average particle size of CuO, Co₃O₄ nanoparticles and their composite was estimated by using Debye Scherrer formula which is found at 18.5nm, 18.1nm, and 17.5nm respectively

FESEM image of CuO nanoparticle are having flake-like structure, SEM image of Co₃O₄ nanoparticle and composite (CuO/Co₃O₄) are in agglomerated with irregular shape.

Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) technique measures size distribution of particles. The particle size distribution of CuO, Co₃O₄ nanoparticles and their composite (CuO/Co₃O₄) are having diameter range 1-10nm, 10-100nm, and 10-100nm

Keywords:

Copper Oxide, Cobalt oxide Nanoparticles, XRD, EDX, DLS, Sol-Gel Process

Probing Surface Chemistry of Cerium oxide Nanocrystals as a function of Capping for their ROS attenuative role and Peroxidase-like activity

Benazir Chishti, Z.a. Ansari, S.g. Ansari

Jamia Millia Islamia, Centre For Interdisciplinary Research In Basic Sciences, India

Email: saansari@jmi.ac.in

Abstract:

With the capabilities to manipulate structures at nano-scale, upsurges deliberate and accidental human exposures. Impediment amid the intracellular biological interactions of metal oxide nanoparticles attributes to generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) thus alarm to elucidate noxious profiling. Herein, adopting wet-chemical approach employed cerium (+3) precursor salt with chloride as counter-ions to synthesize cerium oxide nanocrystals (CeO₂ NCs) and investigated the ameliorative effect of capping (sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS); Triethanolamine (TEA)) in alleviating oxidative stress upon oxidative insult (using H₂O₂) against Gram +ve (Staphylococcus aureus) and Gram -ve (Escherichia coli) bacteria. Further the impact of capping on the peroxidase (POD) mimic catalytic efficiency of CeO₂ NCs was assessed, Figure 1.

The as-synthesized powder was characterized (using FESEM, XRD, XPS, UV-Visible, Raman-scattering, FTIR and zeta potential) for morphological, structural, elemental, functional, optical and surface charge properties. At physiological pH when subjected to oxidative insult (H₂O₂; 0.4mM) compared to pristine, cells pre-treated with capped NCs exhibits strong biocompatibility as revealed from growth profile analysis, minimum inhibitory values suggest non-toxic behaviour of capped NCs against both the bacteria. Compared to positive control (Organism+H₂O₂) a concentration dependent attenuation in the ROS level was observed, with amine (TEA) capping in CeO₂ NCs showed efficient ROS-scavenging activity against both the bacteria. Alleviated cell survivability in presence of inducer towards capped CeO₂ NCs advocate capping in CeO₂ NCs do not diminishes its antioxidative property (1). Over HRP, Kinetic studies reinforce capping in CeO₂ NCs does not impede POD mimic behaviour. Further experiments corroborates the effect of capping on cell viability, lipid peroxidation and oxidative species involved TMB oxidation. Envisioned to manage oxidative stress, current study establishes a correlation amidst shape, size, oxidation state, surface potential, capped-moiety and its concentration to accommodate a prototype towards safer-by-design therapeutic nanomaterials.

Keywords:

CeO₂ NCs, capping, H₂O₂, ROS, peroxidase.

Figure 1: Exemplifies how the research question is addressed: Exploiting redox property and capping in nanosized cerium oxide to bridge the gap between causes of oxidative stress via constructing biocompatible nanostructure based on structure-activity relationship, assess peroxidase biomimetic activity.

Plasmonic nanorattles: an emerging platform for catalysis and SERS based sensing applications

P. Singh, A. Jaiswal

Indian Institute of Technology Mandi, School of Basic Sciences, India

Abstract:

The recent development in the design and synthesis of novel plasmonic nanostructures have drawn significant attention due to their variety of applications in sensing, catalysis, photonics and theranostics. In particular, nanostructures with multiple facets and having defined interior gaps along with their hollow and porous morphology are of great significance for catalysis and SERS applications. Plasmonic nanorattles are the class of hollow, porous core-shell nanostructures which composed of a solid core and a porous thin shell. In this context, we have designed different plasmonic nanorattles of gold-gold, gold-palladium where a solid gold core is surrounded by a thin porous shell of gold or palladium metals respectively. Firstly, we report the synthesis of gold nanorattles comprising of an octahedral core surrounded by a thin porous gold shell through galvanic replacement of a silver nanocube containing an octahedral gold core. Later, we report the synthesis of bimetallic gold-palladium nanorattles comprising of a gold octahedral core surrounded by a thin porous cubic palladium shell. Further, we demonstrated the catalytic activity of these two nanorattles against the degradation of few environmental pollutants such as p-nitrophenol and azo dyes (congo red and methylene blue). Kinetic data of our study indicates that our proposed catalysts are catalytically more active than previously reported metal nanocatalysts. Next, we exploited our bimetallic gold-palladium nanorattles against ORR applications. Compared with commercialized Pt/C, our proposed gold-palladium nanocatalyst displayed nearly comparable onset and halfwave potential values and excellent durability upon potential cycling. Finally, we report the synthesis of gold nanocapsules having a solid Au bead as core surrounded by a thin-porous rod-shaped shell. Using nanocapsules, we designed a simple flexible cellulose-based SERS substrate and investigated its SERS sensing ability for the detection of trace level analytes using 2-NT as a model analyte where we achieved sensing down to 1 fM concentration.

Keywords:

Plasmonic, nanorattles, catalysis, SERS, sensing, galvanic replacement, theranostics, ORR, fuel cells.

Phytosomes: emergent promising nano Vesicular drug delivery system for targeted tumor therapy

Abdul Azeez and V.Sudarshana Deepa

Nanobiotranslational Research Laboratory, Bannari Amman Institute of
Technology, India

Abstract:

Targeting the tumor tissues in oncotherapeutics is attracting more attention worldwide for the last three decades. The exigent need to reduce the side effects of the drugs presses the need for the advancements in the targeting therapies and better alternative to the conventional chemotherapies. The effective bio compatible bioactive compounds that are appropriate substitutes to the conventional anti-cancer drugs face the difficulty in being transported across the cell membrane as they are hydrophilic. In this article the nano vesicular drug delivery system, one of the well- received approaches for targeted drug delivery is reviewed, more specifically the phytosomes. Phytosomes are the unique class of vesicular drug delivery systems that carry the plant derived bio active compounds across the cell membrane.

Phytosomes are micelles capable of encapsulating the plant extracts in the core and conjugating the targeting proteins on the outer surface. Vesicular drug delivery systems in common are passive targeting drug carriers by evading the immune system. But in the case of tumor therapy, due to enhanced permeation and retention effect the phytosomes that are more than 40 kDa and a nano-metric size range of 100–1200 nm target the tumor cells actively. Passive targeting increases the bioavailability of the drugs and the active targeting specifically delivers the drugs in the site of action are coupled in phytosomes to deliver the bioactive compounds. In the presentation the synthesis, properties and drug encapsulation and delivery mechanisms of the phytosomes will be discussed.

Keywords:

Drug delivery, phytosomes, drug release

5-Fluorouracil And Its Inclusion Complex Synthesized Au Nanoparticles For Drug Delivery

Jaya Lakkakula,^{1,3} Rui W.M.Krause², Deepika Divakaran³, Rohit Srivastava³ and Sagar Barage¹

¹ Amity Institute of Biotechnology, Amity University, India

² Department of Chemistry, Rhodes University, South Africa

Abstract:

5-Fluorouracil (5-Fu) is an anticancer drug used for treatment of several cancers. A great deal of research has been carried out on site specific delivery so as to reduce systemic-side effects to therapy. To prolong the circulation time and increase the solubility of 5-Fu and control delivery, we have attempted to modify its delivery by the use of cyclodextrin by forming an inclusion complex with 5-Fu. We report the synthesis of a 1:1 2HP β CD-5Fluorouracil (2HP β CD-5Fu) inclusion complex and adhesion of gold nanoparticles onto the inclusion complex. The synthesis of inclusion complex was confirmed by FTIR, NMR and XRD analysis. The structural vibrations of C=C, C-N and C-F from 5-Fu were clearly observed in 2HP β CD-5Fu complex. The ¹H-NMR investigations suggested that 5-Fu was included within the 2HP- β -CD cavity and H-5 proton probably serves as the binding site for the stabilization of the inclusion complex. Additionally, molecular docking studies confirmed the occupancy of 5-Fu within the hydrophobic cavity of Cyclodextrin along with the hydrogen bond interactions (Figure1). Further the addition of gold nanoparticles on inclusion complex was confirmed using UV-Vis, TEM and FTIR and SEM analysis. The average size of the 2HP β CD-5Fu+AuNps was found to be 18 nm. This unique system with AuNps and Cyclodextrin can serve as a novel delivery system for encapsulation and as a nanocarrier for hydrophobic drugs.

Keywords:

Cyclodextrin, fluorouracil, inclusion complex, gold nanoparticles, hydrophobic drug, anti-cancer, drug delivery, protein folding, biomedical applications.

Novel Nanostructured Materials for Biomedical Applications

Nandakumar Kalarikkal

International and Inter University Centre for Nanoscience and Nanotechnology & School of Pure and Applied Physics ,Mahatma Gandhi University , India

Email: nkkalarikkal@mgu.ac.in

Abstract:

Nanoscience and Nanotechnology research has made significant contributions addressing issues related to many field in particular in the area of biomedical applications. Hybrid nanostructures are found to be much more promising as we can integrate the properties of the constituents and achieve synergetic effects. One of the most promising aspects of the emergent field of polymer nanostructuring is the ability to generate a variety of different morphologies with structural definition on the nanometric scale. The properties and behaviors of the nanostructured materials depend on both, the nature of its molecular constituents and their precise spatial positioning. In this talk, the results of our recent works on Synthesis, antibacterial, cytotoxicity and sensing properties of starch-capped silver nanoparticles, biodegradable electrospun membranes of PCL and P(VDF-TrFE) polymers containing ZnO, TiO₂ nanoparticles and Europium Hydroxide nanorods as skin substitutes with microbial barrier and wound healing properties, in-vitro cytotoxicity and cellular uptake efficiency of zidovudine-loaded solid lipid nanoparticles modified with Aloe Vera in glioma cells and alginate nanoparticles for effective anti-viral drug delivery will be discussed. The potential applications of PMMA/Metal/Metal oxide polymer nanocomposites in Nanodentistry will also be highlighted.

Keywords:

Medical scaffolds, Drug delivery, Polymer nanocomposites, Metal nanoparticles, Metal oxide nanoparticles

Regional network analysis for nanomedical data science

D. Korenblum

Nanobio.md, San Francisco, USA

Abstract:

Network data analysis is emerging as a central tool in biomedical data science¹ having many potential nanomedical applications. However, there is no theoretical consensus on the best way to extract meaningful knowledge from graphs or networks. Therefore, interpretable and rigorously justified methods are important. Recently, Laplacian mixture modeling was introduced² to address this problem and provide a more rigorous definition for network analysis. This algorithm enables a new type of globally optimized, nonhierarchical regional network analysis. Regional network analysis is a new tool for graph/network analysis, avoiding the hard cuts and hierarchical or recursive splittings used by most other methods, to reveal the hidden global structure of the graph or network. This method is illustrated using the synthetic example shown in Fig. 1. The points were mapped to a weighted graph adjacency matrix, and then a Laplacian mixture model was computed for these similarity networks. In this example, each region of the graph corresponds to an actual geometric shape in 2D for the sake of visualization. There is nothing specific about the circular shapes used in this example – they could be replaced with almost any other shape – and also the points can represent nodes in a network. To every point, the model assigns a regional centrality score, indicating the proximity or distance of each point to each of the 4 regions or mixture components defined by the model. Regional centrality scores for each point with respect to each region are identified, providing rankings of how central each point is to each of the regions, defining a type of abstract internal network geometry. Rows 2-5 indicate regional centrality scores by color intensity, from which the shape information is inferred. Regional centrality can be interpreted in terms of a physical heat or diffusion process on the underlying graph structure. It works for arbitrary shapes, including more abstract structures such as biological interaction networks, internet web graphs, etc. E.g., the points in Fig. 1 can also be thought of as representing biological molecules in a physiological model. Detailed nanomedical applications of biomedical network data science are also described.

Keywords:

Biomedical networks, data science, regional network analysis, nanomedical applications.

Multifunctional Polymeric Nanocomposites

Soney C George

Center for Nanoscience and Technology, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering, India

Abstract:

Polymer nanocomposites are potential materials that found versatile applications in automobile, aerospace, electronic and electrical industries. It also improves the human life in a marvelous way. Keen researches are taking place in the field of development of nanocomposite. It is a challenge before material scientists to select the right nanoparticle for improving the properties of polymeric nanocomposites. Nanoparticles such as nanoclay, carbon nanotubes and graphene were revolutionized the polymer nanocomposite industry worldwide. A systematic investigation was done with different types of polymeric matrices to examine the role played by nanoparticles in making them mechanically sound, thermally stable and conductive nanocomposites [1]. Simple two roll mixing technique was used for preparing the elastomeric nanocomposites based on nanoclay and graphene. Solution casting method was used for preparing polymeric membranes. The detailed investigation revealed that the dispersion and morphology of the composite played a significant role in property enhancement of the composites [Figure 1]. Polymeric nanocomposite membranes were fine tuned to improve the flux and selectivity so that it reflected in the separation efficiency [Figure 2].

Keywords:

Nanocomposites, graphene, nanoclay, membrane, morphology, dispersion, interaction, Elastomers, pervaporation separation, liquid mixtures, azeotropic mixtures, flux, selectivity

Figure 1: The dispersion of RGO in elastomeric nanocomposite

Figure 2: Figure illustrating the fundamental principle of pervaporation process by which selective permeation of water molecules took place through the nanoclay/polymer matrix.

Modified Carbonate Apatite Nanoparticles-Facilitated in vitro Delivery of siRNA(s) Targeting Calcium Ion Channels Kills Breast Cancer Cells

Mohammad Borhan Uddin¹, Mohd Farooq Shaikh¹, Mark M. Banaszak Holl² and Ezharul Hoque Chowdhury¹

¹Jeffrey Cheah School of Medicine and Health Sciences, Monash University Malaysia

²Department of Chemical Engineering, Monash University, Clayton Campus, Australia

Abstract:

In breast cancer aberrant Ca²⁺ signalling and intracellular Ca²⁺ homeostasis have been proposed as crucial events in tumorigenesis. Dysregulated calcium influx and efflux has been shown to enhance survival, malignant angiogenesis, excessive proliferation, cell migration and metastasis in various cancer cells namely prostate, hepatocellular and non-estrogen-sensitive breast cancers [1-2]. Despite rapid development in the past twenty five years in exploring the ion channel functions in relation to cancer, most of the mechanisms accounting for the impact of ion channel modulators on cancer growth have yet to be fully clarified.

The development of efficient siRNA nanocarriers for systemic delivery represents an important goal in cancer therapy. The properties of an ideal nanoparticle (NP) for this purpose would include the capacity to remain in the circulation, deliver the siRNA payload to the target organ, interact with the cell surface, enter the cell and finally, efficiently escape the endosome-lysosome system to unload the siRNAs within the cytoplasm [3-4].

Carbonate apatite (CA) nanocrystals basically made of an inorganic cation (calcium) and inorganic anions, namely, carbonate and phosphate possess both anion- and cation-binding domains, enabling them to bind to negatively charged siRNA molecules [5]. Modified CA particles were synthesized with different concentrations of carbonate or phosphate, in the presence of fixed concentration of calcium salts.

In this study, the average diameter of the particles was determined using Zetasizer and FE-SEM. Subsequently the stronger binding affinity and significant cellular uptake of the negatively charged siRNA were observed by quantifying fluorescence intensity. Cell viability was also assessed by MTT assay. Carbonate apatite nanoparticles were individually complexed with five different siRNAs (TRPM7, TRPM8, SLC41A1, SLC41A2 and MAGT1) targeting specific calcium ion channels and transporter genes, and used to treat different breast cancer cells in order to suppress the expression of each of the transporter proteins and evaluate their potential as therapeutic targets for treatment of breast cancer. Hence, modified carbonate apatite nanoparticles with greater surface area [6] have significantly enhanced cytotoxicity in different breast cancer cell lines by enabling stronger binding and more efficient cellular uptake of some of the siRNA(s) mentioned above. These potent therapeutic targets should be further validated in an animal model through systemic delivery of specific siRNAs using the nanoparticles.

Modern Trends in Pharmacy Education: Team Based Learning & Institutional Research

Mehul B. Vyas, Shraddha J. Parmar, Dr. Bhavna Patel, Dr. Samir Shah

Sardar Patel College Of Pharmacy, India

Abstract:

Objective: To ensure that pharmacy education has a global voice.

Background:

Globally, pharmacy educators face challenges in producing pharmacy graduates who meet stakeholder requirements for each country's specific job market. So it is necessary to strengthen the pharmacy education.

Obstacles/ Current Challenges:

The quantity and quality of educators and preceptors are both essential to the success of pharmacy professionals' education. It is difficult in developing countries where there is a lack of resources, expertise, and infrastructure. One of the most critical challenges to empower the system is how to remove the old methods and old strategic learning. Rather we can say how to replace the students from passive learner to active participator.

Steps to strengthen or improve:

To empower the education Team based learning (TBL) and institutional researches are two very important aspects. The TBL strategy can be used and if compared with the old strategies, it may enhance the interest of the students. Institutional research must play a critical role in informing practice and policy within pharmacy education.

Conclusion:

Education strategies should be innovative for the needs of the community in order to optimize effectiveness. This further supports the importance of the adoption of a vision and action plan for global pharmacy.

Bioactive PVA/Alginate/Hydroxyapatite films for controlled release of amoxicillin for the treatment of periodontal defects

Prakash Jayabal

Prakash.J Research scholar, Department of Nanotechnology SRM University, India

Abstract:

Presently, local antibiotics are used for the treatment of periodontal diseases as it has minimal side effects. Polymeric drug delivery system lacks in bioactivity and the patient needs bone grafting in the infected areas as there will be a periodontal loss. Hydroxyapatite (HAp) is a bioceramic which has a wide range of medical applications for bone diseases and periodontal regeneration. In our present work Hydroxyapatite (HAp) nanoparticles incorporated with polyvinyl alcohol-sodium alginate (PVA-SA) films were developed and used as a bone substitute for treating infrabony periodontal defects. Fabricated particles and patches were characterized by XRD, FTIR, and TEM. Polymeric films were analysis for hemolysis, swelling study, drug realizes and antibacterial assay. Amoxicillin is used as the antibiotic. Amoxicillin is added to the HAP/polymer blend and the drug release was studied. Amoxicillin helps in healing the infection while HAP NPs helps in periodontal regeneration.

Keywords:

Bioceramics; Drug Delivery; Amoxicillin; Periodontal infections; Polyvinyl Alcohol-Sodium Alginate; sustained release.

Fabrication of optimized *Ocimum sanctum* synthesized Silver nanoparticles for burn wounds

Richa Sood^a, Dimple Sethi Chopra^b

^aMallige College of Pharmacy, India

^bDepartment of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Drug Research, India.

Abstract:

The present study deals with sequential optimization strategy based on box-behnken method to optimize the process variables for efficient production of *Ocimum sanctum* synthesized silver nanoparticles using biological synthesis. Four substantial factors influencing the dependent variables viz size, zeta potential, Polydispersity index (PDI) and yield were identified as silver nitrate concentration, temperature, amount of plant extract and stirring speed as independent variables. The contribution of the studied factors in monitoring dependant variables were evaluated via analysis of variance. The validity of the model developed was verified, and the statistical analysis showed that the optimal operational conditions were AgNO₃ concentration 5.29mM, temperature 60°C, agitation speed of 500 rpm and plant extract 2.24% (w/v) which primes to form silver nanoparticles of smallest size 83.41 nm and 0.24 with maximum zeta potential of -20.20 and Yield of 18.62. In addition, the optimized AgNPs were characterized using DLS, TEM, FE-SEM and UV-vis analysis. The topical formulation was prepared by incorporation of optimized AgNPs into the carbopol gel base. Further, the gel was evaluated in vivo using the rat model of skin wound healing. The measurement of the wound areas was performed on 2nd, 4th, 6th, 8th, 10th, 12th and 14th days and the percentage of wound closures were calculated accordingly. By the 14th day, silver nanoparticle gel showed 96.20% wound healing activity compared with that of the standard as well as control base. The antibacterial inhibitory efficiency of prepared nano gel was found similar to the commercial product against the *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*.

Keywords:

Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs); characterization; nanogel; wound healing

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the antibacterial activity of silver nanoparticle dressing.

Boron Nitride Based Membranes for Environmental Applications

Cheng Chen, Jieming Wang, Dan Liu, Weiwei Lei

Institute for Frontier Materials, Deakin University, Australia.

Abstract:

Two dimensional (2D) nanomaterials based membranes have been widely developed to solve the environmental crisis and water shortage since the discovery of graphene nanosheets. Among various 2D nanomaterials, boron nitride (BN) - alternatively constituted with boron atom and nitride atom in microstructure - stand out due to their intrinsic chemical resistance and thermal resistance. However, the exfoliation and disperse of BN nanosheets challenge the BN nano-material for membrane preparation.

Here, we develop a ball-milling method to synthesis the amino functionalized BN nanosheets with urea as an agent. After washing with distilled water for 2 week, the obtained BN dispersion with high concentration (5 mg/mL) can be stable for more than half one year. The thickness of the BN membranes can facially be changed by filtering different amount of BN dispersion. The BN based membranes show an improved permeation as the viscosity of the solvents deceased. Furthermore, the BN based membranes exhibit a high rejection rate after soaked in acidic, alka-line and oxidative media for up to one month. More importantly, the BN based membranes show high flux and selectivity for solute screening in aqueous solutions, as well as in organic solutions. The intralayer space between BN nanosheets accounts for such high rejection perfor-mance and the nanosized BN nanosheets contribute to the high flux. This provides the BN based membranes with beneficial properties for practical separation and purification processes.

Keywords:

2D, boron nitride, membrane, ball-milling, flux and selectivity,

Figure 1: Preparation of the BN based membrane and solute separation mechanism. (a) Photograph of BN dispersion (b) Photograph of BN based membrane (c) Cross-section of BN membrane (d) The mechanism of the solute screening.

Nano dispersions for Rubber Compounding: Optimization of Process Parameters

Dr. Siby Varghese

Joint Director, Rubber Consultancy Division, Rubber Research Institute of India, India

Abstract:

Nano-dispersions and emulsions have got wide acceptance in rubber industry. High activity, good transparency, less environmental issues are the added advantages of these materials. It has been reported that nano-dispersions can offer remarkable improvements in the adhesive properties. The solvent based conventional adhesives can be completely replaced by water based adhesives with suitable nano-additives. Polymer nanocomposites reinforced by relatively small amounts of ultra-fine, nano-particles (most often clay platelets) proved exceptionally promising engineering materials with unexpectedly high stiffness/toughness ratio, gas barrier properties, flame retardance, etc.

Graphene related materials such as exfoliated grapheme oxide and reduced grapheme oxide recently achieved much interest in nanocomposite research. Polymer grapheme nano-composites showed excellent conductivity at lower percolation threshold. Addition of rubber chemicals as fine particle dispersions in latex technology will improve the product clarity and also will reduce the rejection rates in thin walled products like gloves, condoms etc. Presence of various chemicals and the processing conditions need to be fine-tuned to ensure maximum share of fine particles in the dispersion. Accordingly the role of surface active agents their doses and the zeta potential of diapered phase and the effort to disintegrate the agglomeration etc. were explored.,

The study is focused on the different methods used for the preparation of Nano-dispersions and their applications in the rubber industry, electronics etc.

Keywords:

Nano dispersions, Latex technology, Ball-milling, emulsions, rubber technology, natural rubber latex

Figure 1: Cumulative size curves of un-milled ZnO and after 6, 12 and 24 hrs of wet ball milling

Bioinspired hydroxyapatite nanoparticles of bisphosphonate for effective treatment of osteoporosis

Sushama Talegaonkar

Department of Pharmaceutics, School of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Delhi
Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research University, India

Abstract:

The major obstacle that limits the successful use of orally administered pamidronate includes low permeability and more importantly, insufficient and fluctuating bioavailability. This poor bioavailability (<1%) of Pamidronate results in the supplementation of high doses that may perhaps lead to severe side effects like Osteonecrosis of the jaws, fever, vein irritation, general aches and pains and kidney dysfunction. Hydroxyapatite based Poly (D, L-lactide-co-glycolide) (PLGA) and polyethylene glycol (PEG) nanoparticles of Pamidronate that target bone tissue was prepared by in-situ polymerization with dialysis method for treatment of osteoporosis.

Pamidronate was conjugated to PLGA via carbodiimide chemistry. Mono-methoxy PEG (mPEG)-PLGA block polymers were synthesized and used to impart surface hydrophilicity to nanoparticles to avoid its uptake by reticuloendothelial system (RES). The structure of prepared di block copolymers were characterized by FT-IR and NMR spectrometry. Pamidronate was adsorbed on the surface of hydroxyapatite (PAM-HA) and it was conjugated with different ratios of mPEG-PLGA. The formation of surface-modified PLGA nanoparticle prepared with various ratios of pamidronate as well as hydroxyapatite and mPEG was confirmed by ¹H NMR and FT-IR spectrometry. Pharmacokinetic study was also performed in Male wistar rats in order to evaluate the efficiency of prepared nanoparicles over existing marketed preparation.

Size and % entrapment of the prepared nanoparticle was found to be 75.3 ± 2.3 nm and 90 ± 3.1 %. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) revealed that mPEG-PLGA-PAM-HA nanoparticles possess smooth and uniform surface. ¹H NMR and FTIR analysis were performed for confirmation of structural integrity of nanoparticles. In vitro release study was performed in PBS pH 7.4, demonstrated slow and sustained release properties of ca(Fig 1) and. 85 ± 2.2 % drug was released in 160 hours from prepared nanoparticles Histopathological studies have also revealed significant restoration of bone structure. Pharmacokinetic study showed a significant enhancement in Bioavailability (2.5 fold) when compared to marketed preparation

Conclusions: The results strongly implicated that mPEG-PLGA-PAM-HA has a therapeutic benefits over pamidronate sodium monotherapy for the treatment of osteoporosis in a rat model. This research is likely to be helpful in the design of functional nanoparticles for the site-specific drug delivery in the treatment of bone diseases.

Keywords:

Osteoporosis, Pharmacokinetic, bioavailability, Volume bone density, Bisphosphonates

Figure 1: In-vitro release of mPEG-PLGA-PAM-HA nanoparticles in PBS pH-7.4

Comparative Study of Nanocatalysts FeS₂ and FeSe₂ for Molecular Hydrogen Evolution Reaction

Shwetharani R, D H Nagaraju, R Geetha Balakrishna

Centre for Nano and Material Sciences, Jain University, India

Abstract:

Hydrogen generation through electrocatalytic water reduction using copious and scalable electrocatalyst is one of the potential methods to produce clean energy. Transition metal dichalcogenides with appropriate band potential have been demonstrated as potential electrocatalysts for hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). Here in we have synthesized nanostructured FeS₂ and FeSe₂ that possess defined and irregular shaped flower like morphology using solvothermal reduction method. X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) confirms the pyrite FeS₂ (iron disulfide) and orthorhombic phase FeSe₂ (iron diselenide) and compared it's HER catalytic performance. FeSe₂ exhibited lower over potential of 113 mV with a current of 2 mA/cm² (10 mA/cm² current at 244 mV) compared to FeS₂ with over potential 453 mV. The improved catalytic behavior of FeSe₂ can be attributed to favourable bond strength between selenide and hydrogen (276 kJ/mol) which is about 87 kJ/mol lesser than FeS₂ (363 kJ/mol).

Keywords:

FeS₂, Electrocatalyst, H₂ evolution, FeSe₂, Transition metal dichalcogenides,

Recent Advances In Nanoscience And Nanotechnology

Dr. Thomas O. Mensah
Georgia Aerospace Systems, USA

Abstract:

Recent advances in Nanoscience and Nanotechnology have shifted emphasis to include commercialization of products and processes because of the tremendous investment in this technology over the past decades.

The Challenges facing commercialization and scale up efforts necessary to transition laboratory research and innovation to useful commercial and military products will be examined. Examples in areas of application to commercial products like Cell phone batteries that last more than two weeks without charging, Internet of things (IOT) Devices for controlling Home Appliances, Food Packaging Films as oxygen barriers for longer shelf life will be discussed.

Finally Military products like Unmanned Aerial Vehicles, Armor Tanks and Body Protective Armor, Missile and Space Vehicle Structures will also be presented. Techniques for Speedy commercialization of Nanotechnology and Nanoscience products and processes will also be presented.

Optical and Electrical properties of Cu-ZnO Prism Shaped Nano Crystals by Microwave Combustion Method

C. C. Vidyasagar

Department of Chemistry, Rani Channamma University, India

Abstract:

Dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) are a low cost and hopeful alternative to standard silicon photovoltaic cells; there is growing interest for near infra red sensitization on semiconductor anode materials, as they offer potential access to an enhanced wide solar energy range to power conversion efficiencies (PCEs). This study proposes that, the effect of ion implantation and annealing temperature could be an effective approach for developing visible-light driven Cu-ZnO anode materials for solar cells, thus it outlines the synthesis of ZnO and Cu doped ZnO nanoparticles via microwave combustion method without using any fuel. The crystal structure, optical properties, surface morphology and electrical properties were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), UV-Visible spectroscopy (UV-Vis), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive analysis using X-rays (EDAX) and Keithley Source meter, respectively. The results reveal that, the change in lattice parameters, decreases in the band gap with absorption peak shifting towards near infra red region are due to change in concentration, annealing temperature and change in crystal defects leads to abrupt change in bond length, unit volume and lattice strain of the Cu-ZnO crystals. Copper phthalocyanine pigment (Imperon Blue-15) sensitized Cu-ZnO films absorbing mainly in the 600-700 nm region have been considered.

Keywords:

Crystal Structure, Doping, Imperon Blue, I-V characteristic, Zinc oxide.

Figure 1: FESEM images of hexagonal pyramid samples prepared ZnO and Cu_{1-x}Zn_xO at different annealing temperature and UV-Vis absorption spectra of Copper Phthalocyanine pigment adsorbed on ZnO and Cu_{1-x}Zn_xO at different annealing temperature. The films were soaked in a dye solution of 0.05 mM dye